

The Strategy of the Local Government in Developing Independent Village Based on Economic and Social Resilience in East Flores Regency

Triwahyuni Ema Goran¹, Setyo Widagdo², Rita Parmawati³

¹National Security, University of Brawijaya, Malang, East Java, Indonesia,+62

²Faculty of Law, University of Brawijaya, Malang, East Java, Indonesia,+62

³Environmental Management and Development, University of Brawijaya, Malang, East Java, Indonesia,+62

Abstract— A qualitative approach with SWOT analysis method is used in this research to explore the reality of the community development in order to realize the village's autonomy in East Flores Regency. It is described through the study of Local Government's Strategy in Developing Independent Village Based on Economic and Social Resilience with the emphasis on the village innovation program as the government's program in realizing Independent Village. The village innovation program is an innovation policy as the government's effort in realizing an independent village through the development of a productive economy based on the potential possessed by the village itself. The result of the research shows that among 229 villages in East Flores, there are only 155 villages joining the village innovation program, and the coordination from the program committee such as the Village Assistants or Village Innovation Team with the village government has not been implemented well. In the commitment decision for this village innovation program, the village government has not comprehended this program so well that it seems that in making the commitment, almost all villages have the same kind of commitment, and in making the commitment the village government also seems not focusing on the potential of the village. Among the 155 villages joining the village innovation program, there are only 43 villages incorporating Village-owned Corporations (BUMDesa) as one of their innovations. Meanwhile, the main target of the village innovation program is the incorporation of BUMDesa as the village innovation. The appropriate strategy in the government's strategic decision in developing independent village by using SWOT analysis is holding a workshop to improve the community capacity using the village fund, Village-owned Corporations (BUMDesa) management, tourism village development, and agricultural product management training. Therefore, the East Flores Regency government needs to monitor and evaluate the implementation of village innovation program so that it will always be accommodated in the upcoming Regional Government Budgets (APBD). The East Flores Regency Government requires to periodically perform capacity strengthening in the form of training and Village-owned Corporations (APBD) optimization as a form of social power and as an effort to improve the economy of the community.

Keywords— Independent Village, Village Innovation Program, Village-owned Corporations.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Law no 6 of 2014 concerning Village (State Gazette of the Republic of Indonesia of 2014 no 7 Supplement of the State Gazette no 5495) clarifies that village development is an effort of the government to greatly improve the life quality and the life of the villagers. Building Indonesia from the rural

area (village) is one of the political commitments aiming to achieve the community welfare and village autonomy. In Law no 6 of 2014 concerning Village, the government tries to give freedom to the head of the village so that the village will be able to be developed by using the democratic system. Therefore, the village welfare can be improved. Moreover, the realization of the economically-independent village that is still environmentally sound, consistent, harmonious, and synergistic with other areas through sustainable development can be realized along with the peaceful, democratic, righteous, competitive, advanced, and prosperous community. However, according to Hanibal Hamidi, et al. (2015) the current condition of Indonesian villages are desperate. It can be seen from the data of Developing Village Index (IPD) in 2015 showing that there are still 15,000 villages becoming the locust of villagers' development and empowerment program implementation, consisting of 5,000 highly underdeveloped villages, 5,000 underdeveloped villages, 2,500 developing villages, and 2,500 developed villages. The indicators of highly underdeveloped and underdeveloped villages according to the Developing Village Index Book of 2016 published by the Villages Development of Disadvantaged Regions and Transmigration Ministry of Indonesian Republic are having a majority of poor villagers, not being economically-independent, not having a well-maintained environment, and lack of access to basic services. Those variables are then converted into 3 indicators, namely economic resilience, socio-cultural, and an independent village. Independent village according to Bambang Brodjonegoro in Harjo (2017) is a village that has its own economic resources, for instance in the agricultural sector or other economic sources, in order to minimize the poverty rate and maximize the access of basic services. Meanwhile, Borni Kurniawan (2015) adds that an independent village refers to the Trisakti Desa, namely sovereign in politics, independent in the economy, and personable in culture.

Hanibal Hamidi, et al. (2015) explains that in Indonesia, according to the Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration Ministry of Indonesian Republic there are 174 villages including in the independent village out of 73,709 of the total villages in 2015. It shows that the welfare of the villagers is still low. It also endangers the social condition of the community for it can trigger potential threats due to the social gap that can affect national security in the

end. The Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration Ministry through the Directorate General of Village Community Empowerment and Development in Hanibal Hamidi et al. (2015) has developed a program expected to be able to strengthen the step of village advancement and autonomy, suppress the poverty level in the village, and develop the resilience. The featured program is developed based on the 3 approaches called as Pilar Desa Membangun, namely Jaring Komunitas Wiradesa, Lumbung Ekonomi Desa, and Lingkar Budaya Desa.

The Government of East Nusa Tenggara (NTT) Province through the Department of Community and Village Empowerment (DPMD) is one of the departments technically in charge of the Village Community Empowerment. Based on the Final Recapitulation of Village Development Status of East Nusa Tenggara Province (NTT) in 2017, the Government of East Nusa Tenggara Province has 3,026 villages spread in 21 regencies/cities with the Developing Village Index (IPD) consisting of 35 developed villages, 591 developing villages, 1,744 underdeveloped villages, and 656 highly underdeveloped villages. Based on the research done by Agustinus Longa Tiza (2014) taking the locust in the Government of East Nusa Tenggara Province, there are several programs launched to improve the advancement and independence of the village. One of the programs is the program of Pembangunan Desa Mandiri Anggaran untuk Rakyat Menuju Sejahtera generally referred to as Anggur Merah that has been started since 2011 by allocating the budget of 250 million rupiahs. The source of the budget is from the Regional Government Budgets (APBD) for each village. This program is expected to help to actualize the independence of the community in developing the village. Independence in planning.

The village dependence on the development programs from the government whether from the Regency/city government, provincial government, or from central government tends to be quite high. It is so dependent on the programs given by the government that the independence and initiative of both the village government and village community are not well-developed. It also happens in the village community in East Flores Regency. The community tends to be dependent on the local government and it waits for the programs given by the local government. In line with the Vision of the Regent of East Flores Regency setting villages as the subject of the development "Flores Timur Sejahtera Dalam Bingkai Desa Membangun Kota Menata", one of the important instruments in realizing it is the formation of Village-owned Corporations (BUMdes). Village-owned Corporations is a village economy organization that can be made as a new step in the government effort in actualizing the village welfare through the village independence. It can also be made as a forum for the community of East Flores in implementing village empowerment and independence. Based on the data of Village-owned Corporations (BUMDesa) in 2018 by DPMD of East Flores Regency, there are 45 BUMDes formed in the East Flores Regency with 229 number of villages which is regarded as insufficient to support the village community of East Flores Regency. According to

Bryan Syaputra (2018), BUMDes as the new pillar of the village economic activity functioning as the social organization, in which the concept of social organization can be explained that all final outcome of BUMDes activities are used for the interest of the community through the contribution in the provisions of various needs and social services. BUMDes must have good relation and/ network with the village community or other parties such as individual, organization, and government institution, in realizing its goals. Such an approach at least explains that BUMDes is an instrument of social capital owned by the village to reach the process of welfare as well as empowerment.

Village assisting done by the Department of Community and Village Empowerment of East Flores Regency tends to be the assistance toward the arrangement of budget planning document in the village. The village community is not empowered to develop the village budget as productive and sustainable economic activity. Almost all villages in East Flores Regency do not have any periodic, productive economic activity that can make its community independent. Based on the phenomenon, the researcher tries to explore the developing problem in the Local Government of East Flores Regency with the research title of "The Strategy of the Local Government in Developing Independent Village Based on Economic and Socio-Cultural Resilience (A Case Study in East Flores Regency)".

The aim of this research is to determine the implementation of village developing program in the East Flores Regency and to analyze the driving and inhibiting factors in developing an independent village.

II. THEORETICAL RIVEW

A. Village and Village Independence

According to the Law no. 6 of 2014 concerning Village, village is a unit of community that has boundaries with the authority to regulate and manage the affairs of government, the interests of local communities based on the community initiatives, the right of the origin, and/or the traditional rights recognized and respected in the system of government of the Republic of Indonesia. R. Binarto (1984) states that the village is the combination of the activity of a group of people with their environment. The result of the combination is the form and appearance in the earth caused by the elements of physiography, social, economic politics, and cultural that interact with each other. Moreover, Moch. Solekhan (2012) adds that a village is a unit of the legal community having the authority to regulate and manage its own interests. It means that the village has its own autonomy right. However, the village autonomy is different from the formal autonomy as possessed by the province, city, and regency government. Its autonomy is only limited to origin and customs.

Based on the Decree of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration Minister No. 2 of 2016 concerning the Developing Village Index (State Gazette of Indonesian Republic of 2016 No. 300), independent village is developed village having the ability to implement the village development for the life quality and life improvement of the village society welfare with sustained social, economy,

and ecology resilience. According to Boni Kurniawan (2015), there are several strategies generally practiced in developing village independence. Firstly, developing the critical and dynamical capacity of the society and civil society organization in the village. Secondly, strengthening the capacity of the government and the dynamic interaction between the social organization and the village government executives. Thirdly, developing the responsive and participative system of village planning and budgeting. Lastly, developing independent and productive local economic organizations.

B. Village Development

According to Yansen (2013), essentially the concept of development is an effort done, in implementing changes or improvement toward a better condition than the previous one. The implementation of the development is done together by the government and community according to the development principles, in which the aims of that development is to bring prosperity and welfare for the community. Tjokromidjojo (1995) describes, in general, the aims of development is nation building or socio-economic development. Furthermore, Tjokromidjojo (1995) states that in the development process there are five necessary dimensions that need to be focused by the actors of development, namely:

- 1) The dimension of community socio-economic welfare, according to the economic point of view, a country is developed if its growth rate is increasing because if the economic growth of a country increases, its social welfare will also increase.
- 2) The dimension of social transformation toward the modern community. In the social transformation toward modernization, there is not only a measurement of knowledge and technology development but also changes in social values in the community.
- 3) The dimension of nation-building. In this concept, the development of a primordial community toward national community is observed. Through the national integration process, the personality, ideology, and nationality insight, including the integration of stability and political participation of the community are developed.
- 4) The dimension of balance. In the environmentally-friendly development concept, the balance and harmony between the life of a human and its environment are greatly required.
- 5) The dimension of human as the focus of the development process. In the positive perspective, development process means the development of human that is more able to develop a better life quality. The aspect of human resource development is not only directed to the improvement of ability and skills, but also to the conducive behavior and attitude for the change toward welfare and progression.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research is a descriptive study with a qualitative approach. This approach is used due to the researcher's curiosity to explore the problems related to the Strategy of the Local Government in Developing Independent Village based

on Economic and Social Resilience in East Flores Regency. The research location is chosen due to the implementation of village budget in East Flores Regency for 4 years, there are only 2 villages assessed as the developed village category out of 229 villages in the East Flores Regency according to the latest recapitulation of Developing Village Index in 2017. The data used are primary and secondary data. The research subjects of this research are the Head of Village Community Empowerment Department, Head of Village Institutional Development Division, Head of Village Economic Development Division, and Head of Socio-Cultural Institution Section.

The data collection methods used in this research are observation, interview, and document. The data are then analyzed by using SWOT analysis in which the available data are processed through data grouping, problem classification, and internal and external factors classification. A SWOT analysis is the analysis of the internal and external condition of an organization which then will be used as the basis to design a strategy and work program in order to make it better. The strategy arrangement by using SWOT analysis is based on the logic to maximize the strength and opportunity, while simultaneously can minimize the weakness and threat as well.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Village Innovation Program

According to the Ministerial Decision of Villages, Development of Disadvantaged Regions, and Transmigration no. 48 of 2018 concerning the General Guidelines of Innovation Program has clearly answered why the Developing Village program supported with the new program which is Village Innovation, the village capacity in implementing the development and perspective of "Developing Village" is realized of still having limitations. That limitation is apparent in the capacity of the village government staffs and community, village management quality, and the supporting system realized in the government regulations and policies related to villages. As the impact, the quality of planning, implementation, controlling, and village construction activity utilization gives less impact on the improvement of villagers' prosperity. Responding to the above condition, the government through The Ministry of Village, Development of Disadvantaged Areas, and Transmigration realize about the deficiency/weakness and improvement efforts related to the issues in pro-active manners, one of them is by launching Village Innovation Program (PID). PID is designed to motivate and facilitate village capacity reinforcement which is orientated to fulfill RPJM target accomplishment as well as the priority program of The Ministry of Village, Development of Disadvantaged Areas, and Transmigration. It is done through the improvement of rural productivity by focusing on local economic development, improving Human Resources quality, and fulfilling also improving rural infrastructure.

In Village Innovation Program, it has been determined the number of commitments/activities for the upcoming year. All determined commitments/activities are the necessity of society in East Flores Regency. There are 301 determined commitments/activities in Commitments List of the fiscal year

2018. The implementation of Village Innovation Program which is newly implemented this year and its implementation are supported by the fund from the World Bank. The allocation and location of the aid fund from the village organizer and knowledge government on Village Innovation Program of the fiscal year of 2018 are Rp 409.995.008.109 (four hundred nine billion nine hundred ninety-five million eight thousand one hundred nine rupiahs) for East Flores Regency itself is given Rp 1.525.371.218 which is then divided into Rp 328.400.000 for Regency Innovation Team and Rp 1.196971.218 for Village Innovation organizer Team. That budget is used for the administration only, not for the funding of Village Innovation activity yet. Among 229 of the total existing villages in East Flores Regency, there are only 155 villages participating Village Innovation Program while the other 74 villages do not participate Village Innovation Program.

All commitment/activity lists made were expected to be supportable for next fiscal year of RKPD and APBD in order to be realizable in the upcoming year. It can be seen from the same type of some commitments/activities made. Every innovation activity was made in the form of training and goods supplying. Another thing noticed from the data is that instead of explaining in detail the type of village innovation, the village government explained it in general, for instance, the case of Hewa village in Wulanggintang sub-district. The innovations offered were village tour, technology, and animal feed, without any explanation on what kind of village tour would be innovation from that village, for what would the animal feed be made, and what technology would be given as the innovation from that village. Those data is approved by village assistance staff that the village government did not explain in detail yet. There were some obstacles found in the Village Innovation activity of "village tour". They were caused by the place that would be made as the tourism object was still in dispute since there were some groups claiming that the tourism object was theirs. Thus, the village innovation was still not explainable by "village tour" nomenclature. It was not clear yet what would be developed as there was no meeting point yet between society group and the village government. Meanwhile, the problem faced for the animal feed was still about tool purchase for manufacturing the animal feed.

The explanation above shows that there should be good cooperation between the society and the village government in implementing Village Innovation Program. However, the society participation level in the Village Innovation Program was not so high in some sub-districts. One of them happened in Hewa Village, Wulanggintang Subdistrict as explained previously. In the village-level meeting, the village government should have discussed all activity programs related to the Village Innovation Program with society. So, in the time commitment/activity construction, the society does not discuss commitment/activity which have been made by the village government. Observing the statement above, except village government, village associate should maximize their duty in facilitating the whole phase of Village Innovation Program activity in subdistrict and village in order the condition such as explained above can be avoided. Based on

the duty and responsibility as village associate, so the continuing coordination should be done with expert staff in the East Flores Regency.

Regarding the target of the village innovation program, there were 229 villages in East Flores district participating in the village innovation program. Nevertheless, the target given in detail was not explained. The head of the village institutional section claimed that in reality, the East Flores district government expected that 229 villages would be able to participate in this village innovation program. In fact, there were no details as stated by the Directorate General of Village Development and Empowerment. However, the course of the program is still maintained even though last year the East Flores district government did not participate in the village innovation program. This year, the East Flores district Government will continue to oversee the program even though there were only 115 villages from 229 villages participated in the program, while the 74 villages did not participate in this program because they did not provide commitments/activities when village innovation exchange was held.

One of the main targets of the Ministry of Village, Disadvantages Area and Transmigration is the development of BUMDesa or BUMDesa herewith; however, among 115 villages that made commitment list on the village innovation market, only 23 villages made BUMDesa village innovation. In addition, for the development of BUMDesa itself in East Flores district since 2013 until now only 45 BUMDesa have been formed out of 229 villages. The development of BUMDesa had been achieved once in 2013 and twice in 2014. The increase was 12 BUMDesa formed in 2015, while the increase of development was 23 BUMDesa formed as well in 2017. However, there was a decrease in 2018 for only 7 BUMDesa were formed. BUMDesa itself is a village business that is formed and owned by the village government, managed independently with capital ownership mostly constituting village assets separated and determined by village regulations.

The activity of PDI was started in August to December 2018. The initial activity was held to form the village innovation team of East Flores district with the legal basis establishment namely East Flores decree number 200 of 2018 concerning the Establishment of District Innovation Team in 2018. The socialization for the introduction of the village program to 229 villages was held in 19 sub-districts along with the sub-district Innovation Team whose legal basis was formed through deliberation forums in the sub-district and confirmed by the sub-district head on behalf of the regent. The implementation of village innovation market was held after socialization in 19 sub-districts. The village head along with 229 secretaries of village attended as participants in the village innovation exchange activities that was carried out by DPMD East Flores District. The result of the activity was the card of innovation commitment that was made by the head of the village along with village secretaries; moreover, the card of innovation commitment became innovation from that program. Furthermore, the implementation of monitoring and evaluation was still carried out by the district innovation team as supervision in carrying out the village innovation program.

B. Supporting and Inhibiting Factors

To find out the internal factors that support and inhibit in building an independent village in East Flores district, the weighting and rating of each indicator have been made. Moreover, the next step is to multiply weighting and rating to obtain the result of total value. The total value will show how to develop an independent village and it can affect the internal factors. Analysis of internal and external strategies are the processing of strategies factor in internal and external environment by giving the weighting and rating to each strategy factor. Strategy factor is the dominant factor of strength, weakness, opportunities, and threats.

The analysis of the internal environment (IFAS) was done to be able to find out several possibilities of strength and weakness. While the analysis of the external environment (EFAS) was done to be able to find out several possibilities of opportunities and threats. The weighting in each environment based on the rate of importance is given 4 scales for very important and 1 for non-importance. Whereas the rating is based on the level of impact with a scale ranging from very large to 1 small.

The analysis of internal factors was started by weighing the strengths and weaknesses factors to build the independent villages in East Flores regency. The weighting was given by 10 respondents.

- The strengths were including:
 - a) Quite a large number of human resources in the village.
 - b) Satisfying utilization of agricultural, plantation, and forestry land.
 - c) Satisfying agricultural and plantation management training.
 - d) Development of tourism areas.
 - e) Accessibility to the development village (19 Districts).
 - f) Availability of education and health access.
- The weaknesses were including:
 - a) The absence of Village Local Revenue (PAD).
 - b) Low quality of human resources.
 - c) Disproportionate travel time with the distance as the road to the village was quite bad.
 - d) Fading value of mutual cooperation.
 - e) Lack of understanding of the community or village government towards village innovation.

The external factor analysis was started by weighing the external factors including the opportunities and the threats with the same respondents.

- The opportunities were including:
 - a) Provision of Village Funds as an effort to increase village development.
 - b) Optimization of Regional Budget as a stimulator of the village economy.
 - c) Allocation of aid funds for the implementation of village innovation programs sourced from the International Bank for Reconstruction and Development.
 - d) Village facilitators formed by the district Innovation Team / Department of Village and Community Empowerment of East Flores Regency.

- e) Created jobs and provided direct benefits to the community.
- The threats were including:
 - a) Lack of attention from village facilitators to village innovation programs.
 - b) Lack of timeliness of implementation of village innovation programs.
 - c) Lack of coordination among village facilitators and village government.
 - d) Village innovation programs that had not been accommodated in the 2019 Regional Budget.
 - e) Lack of coordination among work units related to village innovation programs.

C. External Factor (EFAS/external factor analysis strategy) and Internal Matrix (IFAS/internal factor analysis strategy)

IFAS Analysis or Internal Summary Factor Analysis Strategy consisting of variables of strengths and weaknesses found. These internal factors affect the formation of strength (S) and weakness (W). This factor concerns the conditions which occur in society and the formation of decision makers. Based on the internal analysis of the research area, the IFAS matrix produced is shown in the table below:

TABLE I.

Internal Factor	Weight	Rating	Score
Strengths			
Quite large number of human resources in the village.	0,10	3	0,31
Satisfying utilization of agricultural, plantation, and forestry land.	0,10	3	0,31
Satisfying agricultural and plantation management training.	0,10	2	0,21
Development of tourism areas.	0,10	3	0,31
Accessibility to the development village (19 Districts).	0,10	3	0,31
Availability of education and health access.	0,10	3	0,31
Total			1,76
Weaknesses			
Absence of Village Local Revenue (PAD).	0,07	3	0,21
Low quality of human resources.	0,07	3	0,21
Disproportionate travel time with the distance because the road to the village was quite bad.	0,10	3	0,31
Fading value of mutual cooperation.	0,07	2	0,14
Lack of understanding of the community or village government towards village innovation.	0,07	2	0,14
Total			1,00

IFAS matrix produced the total score for the strength variable of 1.76 which was greater than the weakness variable (1.00). Hence, it can be concluded that the strength variable was more influential than the weakness variable in developing independent villages in East Flores regency.

Whereas, EFAS Analysis or External Factory Analysis Summary Strategy is the external factors that will affect the condition and purpose of the research in term of developing independent villages. EFAS consists of two main factors, namely opportunity and threat variables. Based on the analysis of the external environment at the research site, that EFAS matrix produced is displayed in the table below:

TABLE II.

External Factor	Weight	Rating	Score
Opportunities			
Provision of Village Funds as an effort to increase village development.	0.10	3	0.31
Optimization of Regional Budget as a stimulator of the village economy.	0.10	3	0.31
Allocation of aid funds for the implementation of village innovation programs sourced from International Bank for Reconstruction and Development.	0.10	3	0.31
Village facilitators formed by the district Innovation Team / Department of Village and Community Empowerment of East Flores Regency.	0.10	3	0.31
Created jobs and provided direct benefits to the community.	0.10	3	0.31
Total			1.55
Threats			
Lack of attention from village facilitators to village innovation programs.	0.10	3	0.31
Lack of timeliness of implementation of village innovation programs.	0.10	3	0.31
Lack of coordination among village facilitators and village government.	0.10	3	0.31
Village innovation programs that had not been accommodated in the 2019 Regional Budget.	0.10	3	0.31
Lack of coordination among work units related to village innovation programs.	0.7	3	0.21
Total			1.45

EFAS matrix produced the total score of the opportunity variable of 1.55 and it was greater than the total score of the threat variable (1.45). Thus, it can be concluded that the opportunity variables were more influential than the threat variables in developing independent villages in East Flores Regency.

V. CONCLUSIOAN AND SUGGESTION

Conclusion

- The government efforts in developing independent villages, which were then realized with the Village Innovation program, was a program that aimed to encourage productivity and economic growth in rural areas as well as to build sustainable village capacity to improve the community’s socio-economic welfare and village independence. The village innovation program was the completion of the village building program which was only started this year by East Flores Regency Government. All of the implemented commitments/activities were the society needs in East Flores Regency. Among the total 229 villages in East Flores Regency, only 155 villages participated in the village innovation program, while 74 other villages did not participate in village innovation programs.
- The supporting and inhibiting factors in developing Independent Village were observed from internal and external factors while supporting and inhibiting factors were observed from internal factors as follows:
 - Supporting Factors: Having human resources and empowering them in utilizing agricultural land that can be economic value by

conducting activities in the form of training or technical guidance that is always implemented.

- Inhibiting factors: Lack of village local revenue and low quality of human resources is one of the triggers for inhibiting factors. Moreover, the value of mutual cooperation in village communities has begun to fade. External factors were including:
 - Supporting Factors: The Village Funds as the assistance from the central government as an effort to improve the development in the village is supported by Regional Budget program as a government program in developing the village economy by utilizing local potential through economic institutions.
 - Inhibiting factors: Collaboration and coordination among facilitators and several work units involved in implementing village innovation programs so that there will not be any lack of timeliness are the points that must be noticed. Accordingly, the submitted commitments can be included in Regional Budget of the following year.

Suggestions

Based on the conclusions above, the suggestions from the researcher are as follows:

- The Government of East Flores Regency needs to monitor and evaluate the progress of the village innovation program so that it continues to be accommodated in Regional Budget in the following years.
- The Government of East Flores Regency needs to periodically strengthen the capacity for the actors of village innovation program as an effort to improve community capacity in the form of Technical Guidance. Otherwise, a kind of evaluation activity can be formed to be implemented every 3 months in the District or Village level.
- The Government of East Flores Regency needs to optimize the Regional Budget as social capital and as an effort to improve the economy of the community.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Thank you to the people of the east flores regency and all of you that helped in this research.

REFERENCES

- Hamidi, Hanibal, dkk 2015. Indeks Desa Membangun. Kementrian Desa, Kementrian Desa, Pembangunan Daerah Tertinggal dan Transmigrasi, Jakarta
- Harjo, B. (2017). Model Membangun Desa Mandiri.
- Kurniawan, Borni. 2015. Desa Mandiri, Desa Membangun. Kementrian Desa, Pembangunan Daerah Tertinggal dan Transmigrasi RI, Jakarta
- Peraturan Menteri Desa, Pembangunan Daerah Tertinggal, dan Transmigrasi Republik Indonesia Nomor 2 Tahun 2016. Tentang Indeks Desa Membangun
- Sosial, M., & Coleman, J. S. (2018). BUMDes AL-MADINA DALAM PERSPEKTIF. 1–15.
- Tiza, A. L., Hakim, A., & Haryono, B. S. (2014). Implementasi Program Pembangunan Desa Mandiri Anggaran Untuk Rakyat Menuju Sejahtera (Anggur Merah) (Studi di Badan Perencanaan Pembangunan Daerah Kabupaten Timor Tengah Utara). 17(2), 58–67

- [7] Solekhan, Moch. 2012. Penyelenggara Pemerintahan Desa. Setara Pers. Malang
- [8] Tjokoromijoyo, Bintor, 1995. Perencanaan Pembangunan. Gunung Agung, Jakarta
- [9] Undang-undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 6 Tahun 2014. Tentang Desa
- [10] Yansen. 2013. Gerakan Desa Membangun. Danar Wijaya, Malang